

Beyond Entertainment: Anime on Critical Thinking

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ABSTRACT

Anime is a form of educational entertainment that cultivates learning and develops skills of learners. The aim of this study is to compare the critical thinking ability of learners who are watchers and non-watchers of anime. A total of 87 undergraduate student of San Isidro College were randomly selected to be participants of the study. The study utilized a researcher made questionnaire to assess the critical thinking of the students. The result of the study shows that students spend around 11.8 hours a week watching anime and anime watchers have a higher critical thinking score compared to the non-watchers. Furthermore, the hours spent in watching anime has no bearing on the development of the critical thinking skill due to the few who watched anime for the sake of entertainment.

Subject Areas

Critical Thinking and Educational Technology

Keywords: *Critical Thinking; Anime; Multi-Media; Educational Entertainment*

INTRODUCTION

Technology has been shaping the entertainment industry in the current era and entertainment can be as easy as accessing an app from a phone. The development and creation of multiple applications, sites, and shows are just for the sake of entertainment (Arnold, 2019). The entertainment industry began creating shows that foster learning. The industry combines the concept of a colorful and fun filled experience of a show with the subject based content of a school system (Hassan, Sallehuddin, Aziz, 2016; Schmidli, 2020). School systems have adopted the concepts of entertainment to deliver lessons in class by using movies, shows, and even short-clips. This varied medium of entertainment has helped some students learn and even become proficient in the skill of the subject (The Best Schools, 2016).

Anime is a form of entertainment in the Japanese entertainment industry that typically targets adults and children that ranges from shows to films (Yegulalp, 2018). In the recent years, anime

has grown in popularity and many youths around the world are watching anime series and films. With its continuous development, anime has a broad spectrum of genre that individuals can select from. These ranged from a slice of life to sports to fantasy (Hassan, Sallehuddin, Aziz, 2016; Bond, 2021). The acknowledgment that anime has educational values has surfaced in recent time. Using anime in instruction and as a teaching tool attracts student and creates a fun learning environment (Furo, 2008). Ruble and Lysne (2010) stipulate that using anime engaged and motivated their learners.

Anime has been one of the major genres that has dominated the young generation of today in entertainment. Outside of entertainment, anime has been used to teach different theoretical concepts in the different body of knowledge (Han & Ling, 2017). Many learners are more like to be engaged when there is a story to tell, and anime offers this kind of platform. The story telling narrative can help cultivate the interest of the students and involve themselves in the story (Kincaid, 2018). Due to storytelling, anime enhances the student's creativity and critical thinking. Watching anime is not always about fun, but rather the lessons and learnings that can be acquired and the skills that can be learned from the story or the show (edsys, 2018).

Individuals watch anime for their own reason. May it be to sink themselves in the story, to kill the time or to entertain oneself. Anime can create a system of thinking that organizes reason for liking the show and peers weigh them against each other views, expectations, and hypothesis (Ibblesall, 2014). It is also believed that individuals who watch anime develop critical thinking and analytical skills. The researchers are interested if students who are hooked in anime are more critical thinkers as compared to learners who are do not or are not interested in watching anime. The story telling narrative of anime has been claimed to enhance the creativity and critical thinking alongside among students in their academics (edsys ,2018).

The researchers gave a survey questionnaire to the college students to evaluate their critical thinking and categorized students who watched anime and those who do not and compared their critical thinking score. The study also established the relationship between the critical thinking score and the hours spent by the students in watching anime per week.

CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

This study is based on Educational Entertainment (EE) where learning can take place via mass-media platforms. EE uses multi-media to convey information and foster learning to students. Specifically, the study anchors on visual animation. The study involves measuring the critical thinking of the respondents and gathering data on those who are watchers and non-watchers of anime.

Anime is a type of cartoon which is complex, mature, broader, and even the animation drawing is on a higher level than that of a mere cartoon. Anime, originated in Japan, and drawn by a "*Mangaka*" (artist) into manga (comic) drafts. These drafts are then rearranged, colored and synchronized by a hundred of staff. After the sequencing, a "*Seiyuu*" (Voice Actor) will give life to the character. One second of movement needs twenty-five to thirty-five drafts of drawing. Since it originated in Japan, most of the Animes shows the culture and hidden beauty of Japan, its technological advancement, friendship, love and student's life, the Japanese way (blogspot, 2013).

Critical thinking is the ability of the learners to analyze and come-up with the most feasible solution to a problem. This study has two groups, the groups who are avid anime watchers and the group who are not watchers of anime. Both groups were given the same test and survey questionnaire. Figure 1 illustrates the conceptual schema of the study.

Figure 1. Conceptual schema of the study

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

This study gauged the critical thinking ability of students who watched anime and compared the result with students who were non-anime watcher. Specifically, it answered the following:

1. Is there a significant difference on the scores between students who are watchers and non-watchers of anime?
2. Is there a correlation between students’ score on critical thinking and hours exposed to anime?

METHODOLOGY

This study employed the descriptive research design. The researchers collected data on the critical thinking ability of the students and surveyed information about the habits of students in relation to watching anime. The study was conducted at San Isidro College, Malaybalay City, Bukidnon. The participants of the study were the students enrolled in Mathematics and Statistics during the Academic Year 2020-2021. A total of 87 students were randomly chosen from the list of enrollees as participants of the study.

The critical thinking of the students was measured with a researcher made 40-item multiple-choice questionnaire that has undergone validation and possessed a Cronbach alpha of 0.832. The questionnaire presented a situational type of problem. The data gathered were statistically treated and interpreted based on the result.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Table 1 shows the comparison of the critical thinking score of the students who were watchers and non-watchers of anime based on the result of the survey.

Table 1. Conceptual schema of the study

Group	N	Mean	Standard Deviation	t	p
Watchers	41	31.37	7.522	2.949	0.004
Non-Watchers	46	24.70	12.619		

***p<0.01*

As observed in table 1, the t-values for the anime watchers is 2.949 and for the non-watchers is 3.031 with a probability of 0.004 and 0.003, respectively. The result indicates a significant difference on the critical thinking scores of the students. The difference is also observed in the means of the two groups where the watchers have a mean score of 31.37 which is higher than the

non-watchers who have a mean score of 24.70. The result indicates that student who watched anime have a well-tuned skill in analyzing and making correct decisions to the problems presented to them.

The result is supported by the article of Iblessall (2012) that students who watched anime can develop the skill of critical thinking. This can be attributed to the varied scenarios and plot points in anime where watchers are more likely to interact with the story and hypothesize on the possible outcomes and result of the events. Furthermore, Colon Norat (2017) states that anime can help improve students critical thinking as the visual medial develops the student's ability to interpret the complexity of the themes and issues that they can relate in class or their lessons.

Table 2 displays the association between the critical thinking score and the hours spent watching anime per week.

Table 2. Extent of the association between critical thinking score and hours spent watching per week.

Variable	Mean	<i>r</i>	Extent of Relationship
Critical Thinking Score	31.366	0.142	Negligible Correlation
Hours Spent Watching per Week	11.890		

The product moment correlation was computed and presented in Table 2. The result shows a correlation coefficient of 0.142. The finding is suggestive that the critical thinking score of the students have a negligible correlation to their hours spent watching anime per week. This implies that the hours spent in watching anime shows have no significant impact on the development of the critical thinking skill. The result also suggests that the average number of hours spent by the student is around 11.8 hours per week. The outcome is supported by Colon Norat (2017) and Iblessall (2012) that the individuals' progress in learning and development is according to their pace. Moreover, the study of Tullis and Benjamin (2011) states that individual have their own pace in learning and understanding. The time they spend has little bearing to their development. Furthermore, some individuals only watch anime for the sake of entertainment and do not delve on the deeper scheme of the show or series they are watching (Hassan, Sallehuddin, Aziz, 2016).

SUMMARY

The study established the impact of anime on the critical thinking skill of undergraduate students. The critical thinking score of the students displayed a significant difference between the watchers and non-watchers of anime. The watchers have a higher overall critical thinking score compared to non-watchers.

The survey revealed that learners spend around 11.8 hours watching anime per week. There is negligible correlation when determining the relationship between the critical thinking score and the hours spent watching anime with a coefficient correlation of 0.142. Asserting that the time spent watching anime has no bearing to the development of the critical thinking skill of the students.

CONCLUSION

Anime which is referred to "Japanese animation" has allured many young people to view the show with fervor. Some students have been enthralled by this form of Japanese pop culture such that studying the effects among watchers and non-watchers would be interesting. There are studies

that show anime could increase social interaction especially among anime lovers. There are also findings that students interested in anime pursue an interest in art. In this study, the undergraduate students at San Isidro College, categorized as watchers and non-watchers of anime were compared to whether anime could develop their critical thinking skills; determine the relationships between the critical thinking score and the number of hours spent in watching anime. However, from the findings one can deduce that watching anime has no significant influence on the development of the critical thinking skills of the students. Still, it would be good for Filipino students to be fascinated with other cultures and develop fecundity in the arts, creation of media cartoons, writing story lines, and drawings, that are peculiar to Filipino culture.

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